

A complete aqueous method for trace level extraction and spectrophotometric estimation of Bi(III/V) salts

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Abstract : The extraction and spectrophotometric estimation of Bi(III) and Bi(V) salts were studied in an aqueous polyethylene glycol (PEG) based biphasic system. Na₂SO₄ and MgSO₄ salt rich phases were applied against 50% PEG solutions to obtain the two phase system. The chelating ligand, ammonium pyrrolidine dithiocarbamate (APDC) was used to form a complex with Bi(III) and Bi(V). The complex is found to dissolve in the aqueous solution of polyethylene glycol which can be utilized for the spectrophotometric determination of Bi even at trace level concentrations (~30 mg/L). The yellow colored Bi-APDC solution in PEG shows a wavelength of maximum absorption at 360 nm. Variation of pH of the salt solution in the acidic range did not affect the extraction efficiency much. Bi can be stripped back in the salt rich phase by addition of very dilute alkali that breaks the complex with APDC.

Keywords : Aqueous biphasic system, Bi(III/V) extraction, polyethylene glycol (PEG), APDC.

Introduction

Amongst the heavy and toxic elements in the periodic table, bismuth is considered to be the most benign and is found to pose minimum threat to the environment. Compounds of Bi(III) and Bi(V) have generally very low solubility and are used in cosmetics, as pigments, and a few as pharmaceuticals. Since the toxicity of lead has become more apparent in recent years, alloy uses for bismuth metal (presently about one third of bismuth production), as a replacement for lead, have gained increasing commercial importance. Overexposure to bismuth may certainly cause black line on gums and ulcerative stomatitis. Its biological half-life for whole-body retention is 5 days but it can remain in the kidney for years in patients treated with Bi compounds for a long time¹. On the contrary certain compounds like bismuth subcarbonate and bismuth subnitrate are used in medicine. Bismuth subsalicylate is used as an antidiarrhoeal and to treat some other gastro-intestinal diseases. Also, bibrocatol, an organic molecule containing Bi is used to treat eye infection². Bismuth(V) complexes of lapachol were found to inhibit the growth of a chronic myelogenous leukemia

cell line and this complex was about five times more active than free lapachol³. Industry makes use of bismuth compounds as catalysts in manufacturing acrylonitrile, the starting material for synthetic fibers and rubbers. Isolation of bismuth in different chemical forms is therefore a ubiquitous job for analytical chemists.

Liquid-liquid extraction is one of the most popular techniques employed for recovery of bismuth(III). Earlier, the extraction behavior of bismuth(III) was studied using various methods. The 2-bromoalkanoic acid in benzene and in hexane systems were used against aqueous conditions of high acidity for extraction of bismuth(III)⁴. The other prominent reagents used for this purpose include high molecular weight amines (HMWA) and organophosphorus compounds. *N-n*-Octylaniline and Aliquat 336-S have been used for extraction separation of bismuth(III) from acidic media⁵⁻⁷. Bis(2,4,4-trimethylpentyl)phosphinodithioic acid (Cyanex 301), monoctylanilinobenzylphosphonic acid, tris(2-ethylhexyl)phosphate, triphenylphosphin oxide, bis-(2,4,4-trimethylpentyl)monothio-phosphinic acid (Cyanex 302) are prominent organophosphorus extractants used for extraction of

bismuth(III)⁸⁻¹². A study on bismuth(III) extraction and its separation from other elements was carried out with triphenylarsine oxide¹³. The method was applied for analysis of alloys and pharmaceutical samples successfully; however, triphenylarsine oxide is toxic. Bi(V) in the form of bismuthate was extracted with tetramethylammonium iodide in chloroform followed by direct spectrophotometric measurement at 513 nm¹⁴.

Concurrently the spectrophotometric reagent for bismuth estimation had long been the dithiocarbamates and these are specifically used for extracting bismuth as pyrrolidine dithiocarbamate (APDC) complex or diethyldithiocarbamate (DDC) complex from an aqueous solution into methyl isobutyl ketone (MIBK)¹⁵⁻¹⁸. The complexes being water insoluble need a suitable organic solvent for dissolution.

The above facts indicate that earlier extraction studies offered clean separation and estimation of bismuth but the extraction media used were of organic nature and are inherently hazardous to the environment. In this work for the first time we report a completely aqueous method for extraction and spectrophotometric determination of Bi(III) and Bi(V) at trace concentrations using the reagent APDC. An aqueous biphasic system (ABS) is an aqueous, liquid-liquid extraction system which is obtained either by mixing aqueous solutions of two polymers, or a polymer and a salt¹⁹⁻²². The latter is composed of polyethylene glycol (PEG) and inorganic salts. PEG usually has a far higher concentration in the upper (low-density) phase of such solutions in spite of its inherent density being greater than water. This creates a predominantly low-density water environment due to its partially hydrophobic character, in turn mainly determined by the methylene groups. However, because of their nontoxic, non-volatile properties the consequence of using PEG instead of organic solvents greatly enhances the probabilities of exploring the aqueous chemistry of organic reagents. Here, we report experimental results of liquid-liquid extraction of APDC complex of Bi(III) and Bi(V) using an ABS consisting of PEG in combination with salts like Na₂SO₄ and MgSO₄.

Experimental

The polyethylene glycol (PEG#6000), salts of magnesium sulphate (MgSO₄), sodium sulphate (Na₂SO₄), bismuth nitrate (Bi(NO₃)₃) and sodium bismuthate (NaBiO₃)

were of A.R. grade and obtained from Merck. The complexing agent ammonium pyrrolidine dithiocarbamate (APDC) was obtained from Sigma Aldrich. A double beam Perkin-Elmer Lambda 25 UV-Visible spectrophotometer and a digital pH meter, Systronics (type no. 335) was used for our studies.

Stock solutions of 50% (w/w) PEG, (2 M) MgSO₄, (1.5 M) Na₂SO₄ were prepared. pH of the sulphate salt solutions were adjusted to different values by adding dilute H₂SO₄. A stock solution of 10 mM Bi(III) was prepared by dissolving solid Bi(NO₃)₃ in 2 M HNO₃ medium and it was diluted to 1 mM using water. Stock solution of 1 mM Bi(V) was prepared by dissolving definite amount of solid powder NaBiO₃ in glacial acetic acid. 0.1% APDC solution was prepared in water. To 3 mL aliquot of 50% PEG (#6000) solution, 0.2 mL 1 mM Bi(III) and 0.2 mL APDC solutions were added. 3 mL of salt solutions of respective concentration were added and shaken for 10 min. The upper PEG rich phase having Bi-APDC complex was taken out for spectrophotometric studies (λ_{\max} 360 nm). A prior calibration of Bi(III), solution was performed using APDC in PEG#6000 (50%) along with a blank (PEG#6000 and APDC) to compare the wavelength of maximum absorption. The pHs of the sulphate salts were varied and extractions were carried out in a similar manner. Similar extractions were also performed with 0.2 mL of NaBiO₃ solution. However as Bi(V) decomposes to Bi(III) in presence of strong acids and as the strong acids are used for the lowering of pH of the salt rich phases, the extraction pattern at varying pH conditions of the salt rich phase could not be studied. The complexation of Bi(III/V) with APDC was found to occur in the neutral to acidic pH. The complex was found to dissolve in 50% PEG solution, the solubility of the sparingly soluble salt Bi(NO₃)₃ was determined in water using this method. For this, a known amount of this sparingly soluble salt was dissolved in water and filtered through Whatman 40 to get a clear solution. Measured volume of this Bi-solution was treated with excess APDC solution. The yellow mass which appeared due to complexation was dissolved in 50% PEG solution and taken for spectrophotometric estimation to find out the dissolved concentration of bismuth.

The influence of possible interfering heavy metals in the matrix was examined. The effect of potential interfering ions on the determination of Bi(III) species was investigated by adding known concentrations of different heavy metal ions to the salt rich phase. Bismuth along with the mixture of various ions was then extracted individually with APDC in the PEG rich phase. For this, measured aliquots of the salt solutions of Hg(II), Pb(II), Cd(II), Tl(III) in the nitrate form were taken. The mixture solution was added to the APDC solution taken in PEG along with the Bi(III) nitrate in dilute nitric acid medium. This was extracted against Na₂SO₄ salt rich phase. Partitioning in the PEG rich phase and subsequent measurement were then performed in a similar way described earlier.

Results and discussion

The Bi(III/V) salts form a yellow colored complex with APDC which is insoluble in water and soluble in polar organic solvents¹⁵. Owing to the amphiphilic nature of PEG solutions, the Bi-APDC complex becomes completely soluble in it. A yellow solution results that has a wavelength of maximum absorption at 360 nm (Fig. 1) and the absorbance value at this position steadily increases with

Fig. 1. UV-Visible spectrum of Bi-APDC complex dissolved in 50% PEG solution.

the concentration of Bi in the complex. The formation of Bi(III) and Bi(V)-APDC complex was established by calculating the binding constant of the complex using Benesi-Hildebrand equation.

$$\frac{1}{F - F_0} = \frac{1}{F_1 - F_0} + \frac{1}{F_1 - F_0} \times \frac{1}{K} \times \frac{1}{[M]} \quad (1)$$

$$Y = A + BX \quad (2)$$

where F is the absorbance of the experimental solution containing metal and amino acid, F_0 is the absorbance of the amino acid only. $[M]$ is the metal ion concentration. K is the binding constant. Eq. (1) can be presented in the simple format of eq. (2) where the slope of the graph is given by $(1/F_1 - F_0) \times 1/K$ from which, the binding constant of the complex can be calculated.

The Benesi-Hildebrand plots of Bi(III) and Bi(V) complexes are shown in Figs. 2 and 3, which show that the stability constant of Bi(V)-APDC complex is slightly higher

Fig. 2. Benesi-Hildebrand plot of Bi(III)-APDC complex.

Fig. 3. Benesi-Hildebrand plot of Bi(V)-APDC complex.

($9.7 \times 10^3 \text{ M}^{-1}$) than Bi(III)-APDC complex ($2.3 \times 10^3 \text{ M}^{-1}$). The mechanism of complexation of Bi(III) and Bi(V) with APDC are invariably different and this has been explained using the stability constants (calculated from Figs. 2 and 3), Sandell's sensitivity, molar absorptivity, etc., as presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Differences in the properties of Bi(III) and Bi(V) complexes

Parameter	Bi(III)-APDC complex	Bi(V)-APDC complex
Stability constant (M^{-1})	2.3×10^3	9.7×10^3
Beer's law limit (mM)	0.030–0.111	0.00769–0.09859
Molar absorptivity ($\text{L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$)	1762.5	56567.5
Sandell's sensitivity ($\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$)	275.17	4.9498
Regression equation	$Y = 0.184x + 0.048$	$Y = 0.002x + 0.143$

This fact was also applied to evaluate the solubility of $\text{Bi}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ in water. The maximum solubility of this salt was found to be 450 mg/L at 25 °C. The aqueous biphasic system (ABS) designed by the combination of 50% PEG(#6000) and Na_2SO_4 (1.5 M)/ MgSO_4 (2 M) was examined for its ability to extract the Bi-complex at varying pH conditions. These extractions were performed keeping in mind the pharmaceutical and catalytic application of Bi as described in the introduction section. Both these applications would require Bi at very high purity and free from other ionic contaminants. Liquid-liquid extraction would help us to separate Bi at low concentrations (down to ~30 mg/L) from other contaminants in the salt rich phase. When sodium sulphate was used as the salt rich phase, all the pH conditions from 1–5 were found to offer equally suitable extractions for the Bi(III)-APDC complex (Fig. 2).

However, when magnesium sulphate was used as the salt rich phase, the extractability starts decreasing at pH 4 (Fig. 3). To find an answer, the solution condition of the magnesium sulphate at different pHs were evaluated using the theoretical programme CHEAQS²³. It is revealed that increasing the pH of 2 M magnesium sulphate solution decreases the concentration of free Mg^{2+} ions in the medium. This is also the same for 1.5 M sodium sulphate solution. However, Mg^{2+} lies at much higher position in the Hofmeister series, $\text{Mg}^{2+} > \text{Ca}^{2+} > \text{Sr}^{2+} > \text{Ba}^{2+} > \text{Li}^+ > \text{Na}^+ > \text{K}^+ > \text{Rb}^+ > \text{Cs}^+$ which represents an arrangement of the cations in order of their

salting out ability²⁴. So, as the concentration of free Mg^{2+} ion decreases it can salt out lesser amount of Bi to the PEG rich phase. That is why a lesser percentage of extraction of Bi in PEG is observed at pH 4 of magnesium sulphate salt rich phase.

The Bi(V) salt was dissolved in acetic acid as it is insoluble in cold water and in hot water it gets reduced to Bi(III) as

Bi(V) salt also decomposes when placed in strong acids. The extraction of both Bi(III) and Bi(V) at the same time and at same conditions is therefore not possible. After complexation with APDC the extractability of both Bi(III) and Bi(V) in PEG becomes feasible due to change in hydration sphere around the cations.

The extraction studies of Bi(V) salt using the same two salt rich phases reveals 100% extraction in the PEG rich phase. Since the pH of such systems are comparatively higher thus providing higher amount of free Mg^{2+} ions, which in turn facilitates salting out of bismuth. Bismuth can be stripped back from the APDC complex and hence from the PEG phase by simply elevating the pH to alkaline range (≥ 8). As soon as a very dilute solution of NaOH is added to the PEG solution containing Bi-APDC complex, the yellow color disappears. If this PEG phase is extracted against a fresh batch of sodium sulphate salt rich phase, the Bi is stripped in the lower salt rich phase which can be confirmed by addition of APDC that gives a yellow precipitate confirming the presence of Bi in it.

Addition of interfering salts to the extraction system does not alter the extraction pattern. A list of the added salts along with Bi(III) is presented in Table 2. The results show that the proposed method can be applied to multi-elemental samples that contain other heavy metals at comparable concentrations with bismuth. The reason for non interference of the added salts in the extraction

Table 2. Concentrations of different salts added as interfering agents and their effect on the extraction of Bi(III)

Salts added	Concentration (mM)	Extraction of Bi(III) (0.047 mM) in PEG rich phase
$\text{Hg}(\text{NO}_3)_2$	0.047 mM each	100%
$\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$		
$\text{Cd}(\text{NO}_3)_2$		
$\text{Ti}(\text{NO}_3)_3$		
$\text{Bi}(\text{NO}_3)_3$		

Fig. 4. Extraction profile of Bi(III) salt in PEG rich phase with varying pH of sodium sulphate.

Fig. 5. Extraction profile of Bi(III) salt in PEG rich phase with varying pH of magnesium sulphate.

behavior of Bi(III) is probably due to two reasons. Firstly, the APDC complex of the other cations (Hg^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Tl^{3+}) are colorless and hence do not introduce spectral interference in the estimation of Bi-APDC complex. Secondly, the fact that APDC is taken in far excess than the concentration of the cations and hence complexation and the extraction in the highly concentrated PEG phase remains possible with even larger number of heavy metal cations.

To validate the method further, the acetic acid solution of Bi(v) was taken in PEG medium and APDC solution was added to it in excess. Bi(III) solution in dilute nitric acid medium was added to the same medium and extraction studies were performed as earlier. A proportionate increase in the absorbance value at 350 nm of PEG solution after extraction of total Bi suggests that the method can be used for the extraction of Bi at any of the two oxidation states after a prior complexation with APDC in the PEG medium.

Conclusion :

The APDC complexation of Bi(III/v) salts and subsequent dissolution in PEG solution offers a completely aqueous method of Bi determination spectrophotometrically even at trace concentrations. The aqueous biphasic system also allows quantitative extraction conditions of Bi(III) and (v) in the PEG rich from aqueous medium. The solubility of the sparingly soluble salt of $\text{Bi}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ in water could also be ascertained using this method.

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